

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

D5.7: Tool support for citing and annotating musical scholarly objects

(V1.0)

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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Polifonia develops novel ways of leveraging European cultural heritage to support humanities studies in music. This entails a broad range of activities spanning several domains and technology requirements, reflected on a breadth of research outputs that are both heterogeneous and strongly interconnected. This situation, typical of many large interdisciplinary research projects, such as the ones funded by the H2020 program, opens the challenge of collecting and organising these research outputs (data, software, and tools), to satisfy data management requirements, but allowing stakeholders to explore the wealth of outputs and, therefore, foster reuse beyond the project. We aim at addressing this challenge with a Research Ecosystem.

This deliverable *D5.7: Tool support for citing and annotating musical scholarly objects* presents the results of Task 5 of Work Package 5: *Publishing, accessing and reusing Musical Scholarly Objects*, which aims at making available the wealth of assets of Polifonia for reuse and citation, studying novel methods for collecting and cataloguing research object and its metadata, and methods to enable its annotation describing how it was produced and used within the project activities, covering crucial aspects such as provenance and licensing information. The task aims at supporting the coherent presentation and the discovery of data, software, and resources relevant to future scholarly enquiries. This deliverable focuses on (open source) software, specifications, tools, and live systems implementing an *ecosystem* approach to research data management: the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO). Crucially, we show its application to make available the wealth of assets of Polifonia pilots for citation and reuse: the Polifonia Ecosystem. Finally, we provide an overview of how citability is further supported in different ways by other solutions developed in Polifonia.

The content of this deliverable extends and complements the methodology developed in Work Package 1 by the Technical Board (D1.3 [1]), which was presented and validated in the series of Data Management Plan deliverables (D7.1 [2], D7.2 [3], and D7.3 [4]).

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1 Introduction

Large collaborative research projects bring together technologists who engage in complex software development activities. Compared to open source software, the outputs of research projects are of a special kind. In addition to meeting the requirements of the associated tasks and cohort of users which in research projects naturally change over time, those outputs need to comply with data management requirements, which cover several different aspects such as fine-grained metadata curation, extensive documentation, and publication of the assets for the sake of reuse and reproduction. On the one hand, research outputs can be very heterogeneous in nature, encompassing data files, software programs (experiments, reusable libraries), demonstrators, but also requirements documents or technical documentation such as tutorials and *howtos*. In addition, the need for their description in the context of the research project structure (work packages), scientific methodologies (quantitative/qualitative methods, participatory design), and objectives, raises challenges that go beyond the archival requirements of digital libraries (e.g. Figshare or Zenodo). On the other hand, the collection and curation of research outputs generates a significant overhead to the scientific and development teams, when collecting and harmonising such information constitutes a strong bottleneck for the realisation of healthy data publishing practices (FAIR, 5*Linked Data, etc...).

Since we have entered the Internet age, and digital documentation was augmented to being available in principle around the globe to everybody, inside academia there has been a debate if these new technological opportunities should not be explored to open the black box of the research process and to trace the whole process of scholarly knowledge production. An example for this is the Force11¹ movement. They describe themselves as a "community of scholars, librarians, archivists, publishers and research funders that has arisen organically to help facilitate the change toward improved knowledge creation and sharing."² they have following established a conference series since a Dagstuhl workshop in 2011. This initiative is one of many. Under the umbrella term of *Open Science* we see various cross-domain research infrastructures, such as OPERAS, or the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Around them communities are expanding the existing bibliographic documentation standards for scholarly output such as Dublin Core, but also seek machine readable annotations of *concepts* in scholarly text (see so-called nanopublications [5]) and ontologies to annotate any research object relevant for knowledge production (see RO-CRATE)³.

For researchers who are often also their own documenters this new wave of documentation opportunities, standards-in-the-making together with obligations from funders to require FAIR requirements in Research Data Management Planning can easily lead to an overwhelming situation in which input is requested for Research Information Systems (locally), for portals of the funders (to document progress on a workplan), to data repositories, the publisher's website, the website of the project, and least but not least via social media channels.

For interdisciplinary projects domain specific annotation schemes meet generic documentation requirements and need to be linked to each other.

This deliverable *D5.7: Tool support for citing and annotating musical scholarly objects* presents the results of Task 5 of Work Package 5: *Publishing, accessing and reusing Musical Scholarly Objects*, which aims at making available the wealth of assets of Polifonia for reuse and citation, studying novel methods for collecting and cataloguing research object and its metadata, and methods to enable its annotation describing how it was produced and used within the project activities, covering crucial aspects such as provenance and licensing information. The task aims at supporting the coherent presentation and the discovery of data, software, and resources relevant to future scholarly enquiries.

¹<https://force11.org>

²<https://force11.org/info/about-force11/>

³"A Research Object (RO) provide a machine-readable mechanism to communicate the diverse set of digital and real-world resources that contribute to an item of research. The aim of an RO is to replace traditional academic publication as a PDF with a couple of supplementary materials; to instead provide a structured archive of all the items that contributed to the research outcome, including their identifiers, provenance, relations and annotations" <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/background.html>

In [6] we discuss the problem by proposing *Research Ecosystems*. We define a set of requirements for collecting, curating, and publishing research outputs. In this deliverable, we present a methodology built upon existing good practices for software and research data management. GitHub⁴, the de-facto standard platform for open source, collaborative software development, is used for research assets management, metadata curation, documentation, and publishing. Zenodo⁵ is in turn used as an archive of persistent, versioned research objects releases. On top of these well-known systems, we develop methods and tools to collect, organise, and publish rich metadata, resulting in a catalogue of interlinked research objects: the Research Ecosystem. By relying on well-established software development practices, our method makes it easier to build a collection of research outputs, cataloguing, curating, and publishing them. The approach considers data management requirements including the publishing of versioned assets in open access repositories and the delivery of the components catalogue in a form suitable for human and machine consumption alike, by generating multiple representation of the metadata according to established specifications for metadata interchange (Schema.org primarily).

This deliverable focuses on (open source) software, specifications, tools, and live systems implementing an *ecosystem* approach to research data management: the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO). Crucially, we show its application to make available the wealth of assets of Polifonia pilots for citation and reuse: the Polifonia Ecosystem. Finally, we provide an overview of how citability is further supported in different ways by other solutions developed in Polifonia.

The content of this deliverable extends and complements the methodology developed in Work Package 1 by the Technical Board (D1.3 [1]), which was presented and validated in the series of Data Management Plan deliverables (D7.1 [2], D7.2 [3], and D7.3 [4]).

In particular, we contribute:

1. the Research Ecosystem Framework suite of specifications and tools (REECO), specifically a) The REECO annotation schema b) The REECO annotations validator c) The REECO ecosystem website builder;
2. The Polifonia Ecosystem, which applies the proposed approach, specifically: a) The Polifonia Ecosystem Website b) The Polifonia Ecosystem Knowledge Graph.

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows. First, we describe the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO) and related toolkit in Chapter 2. Next, we show the application of the framework to the Polifonia Ecosystem in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 is dedicated to providing a summary of the Polifonia outputs (Pilots and Tools) from the point of view of how their content can be referenced in scientific publications. Finally, in Chapter 5 we place the contribution in the context of the project data management plan and FAIR principles, before concluding the deliverable (Chapter 6).

⁴<http://github.com>

⁵<http://zenodo.org>

2 The Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO)

In this chapter, we present the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO) that was developed to support the acquisition and management of metadata about outputs of collaborative research projects such as Polifonia.

2.1 Rationale and overview

The main motivation behind the work is the recognition that large collaborative research projects produce a variety of heterogeneous research objects, data, software, and tools. Such activity is well acknowledged by funders that require research consortia to develop data management plans (DMP) to coordinate, organise, and describe research outputs beyond publications. However, the activity of collecting, managing, and presenting research objects is still a challenging task. Ideally, data managers should be keeping track of the outputs produced by work packages and how they are applied to use cases. These outputs consist of data, software, and end-user applications. Furthermore, they should be aware of their reuse in the project. We can summarise the objectives of our work as follows:

- Support Research Data Management: by facilitating the collection and organisation of information about research objects, by identifying and cataloguing outputs;
- Acquiring metadata: support the encoding of fine-grained metadata
- Assess compliance with FAIR principles;
- Present an organised view of project outputs to foster reuse beyond the project;
- Support an aware reuse of outputs by including copyright and licencing information;
- Lower the barrier for users (developers, data scientists, researchers) to provide extensive metadata, building on good practices in (open-source) data/software development and research open data publishing;
- Facilitate the generation of metadata in different forms, to plug-in existing open science distributed infrastructures.

We use the metaphor of an *ecosystem* to guide our approach and coin the notion of *Research Ecosystem*: a collection of components of various types (Data, Tools (software and applications), and Reports) which are built, interconnected, and reassembled in research activities to answer specific research goals. The use of the metaphor of an ecosystem is not new in the sciences, but this concrete approach to trace components of the main types Data, Tools and Reports to enable knowledge and project management at the same time is new.

Following the above definition of a Research Ecosystem, through a collaborative effort involving all partners in the Polifonia project, we designed a framework leveraging good practices in open source software engineering and research data management, building on existing infrastructure:

- GitHub is the primary infrastructure for collaborative open-source software development and it is used by the majority of research software engineers for managing and publishing both software and data;
- Zenodo is one of the flagship platforms of the Open Science community for depositing technical reports, publications, software, and data of research activities. Crucially, its integration with GitHub allows easy publishing (and DOI assignments) of software and data through automated, versioned releases;
- Schema.org is the reference initiative for providing structured annotations to web content, facilitating indexing and retrieval in mainstream web search engines

The Research Ecosystem Framework presented in this deliverable is the technical side of a broader set of activities devoted to collecting, organising, and managing Polifonia outputs, leading to the final Data Management Plan (DMP) [4]. The DMP (version 3) describes the process which led to the final design of the Research Ecosystem, summarises and gives examples of its current components, and details how to use the Ecosystem in the context of Research Data Management.

The Research Ecosystem Framework has been accompanied by conceptual work (the Socio-technical roadmap) and a set of knowledge management instruments tailored to Polifonia's needs (Survey/Stories) [7][8][1].

Here, it is worth summarising the general methodology and workflow that the framework aims at supporting, which includes a number of activities performed during the entire duration of the project. In a nutshell, our approach comprises the following steps:

1. A technical board designs guidelines for managing outputs. These are collected into a Rulebook (see Data Management Plan version 2 for details [4]). The technical board keeps a register of the repositories managed by the consortium (often appearing under the project organisation umbrella (e.g. <http://github.com/polifonia-project>). Each repository has a *champion* who is in charge of curating the content and producing well-documented releases.
2. Developers annotate components directly in the repository following an agreed annotation schema. Annotations are encoded alongside the code in documentation files (e.g. README.md), using the standard techniques of embedding YAML code in the Markdown front-matter.
3. Annotations are collaboratively enhanced in multiple iterations in dedicated workshops organised during the project meetings. In this phase, it is useful to support annotators with dedicated tools to validate the annotations and recommend improvements.
4. Repositories are released and automatically synchronised on Zenodo, which generates DOIs for each one of them.
5. A Research Ecosystem website is developed by collecting, aggregating, and organising the documentation pages and annotations in a harmonised structure. The website includes Schema.org annotations and DOIs, and provides an overview of how outputs have been produced and used within the breadth of activities of the project.

The Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO) was developed to support the workflow deriving from such activity¹. In what follows, we present the REECO toolkit, comprising an annotation schema, a tool to validate annotations, a website builder, and methods for generating Schema.org annotations and knowledge graphs.

All the tools are under a Github organisation `reeco-framework`². Table 2.1 summarises the repositories. For clarification, for the Polifonia project, early on a rulebook has been developed which covered main steps in the development and implementation of the Polifonia Ecosystem (see also the DMP version 2 for the guidelines around the Ecosystem at this time [3]). In the finalisation of the REECO approach (as described in this deliverable) all elements were published as generic (re-usable) tools and workflows.

¹<http://github.com/reeco-framework>

²<http://github.com/reeco-framework/>

Table 2.1: Repositories of the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO)

Annotation Schema	http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-annotation-schema The REECO annotation schema sources and documentation
Python Library	http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-python A software library in Python to help processing and validating annotations. This is reused by various tools.
Web Validator	http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-web-repo-validator A utility to validate the annotations on a repository (running instance at http://reeco.kmi.open.ac.uk).
Action	http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-website-action A custom GitHub action to automate the generation of the ecosystem knowledge graph and website
Website	http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-jekyll A customised Jekyll website template. This includes the custom GitHub action to automate the build process.
Documentation	http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-documentation A repository to collect documentation and pointers for the Reeco framework.

2.2 The REECO annotation schema - annotation of components

In this section we present the REECO Annotation Schema³. It is worth noting that we don't aim at producing a novel metadata schema but at providing support for collecting annotations and generating structured metadata from them. The REECO annotation schema, therefore, is based on a collection of terms that map to well-known metadata sets and, in principle is extensible to cover new requirements. Therefore, we designed the schema by analysing and reusing well-known ontologies and vocabularies in the reference community, namely Schema.org, Dublin Core, PROV-O, and the suite of SPAR ontology for research and data management.

In what follows, we describe the annotation schema by providing a step-by-step guide to produce annotations, which reflect also the content of the workshops we have conducted in the Polifonia project with the researchers and developers. The process is built on incremental steps, here summarised:

1. Preliminaries: set up a GitHub repository
2. Design structure: containers and components
3. Annotation schema terms:
 - Descriptive metadata
 - Resources, releases, and DOI
 - Policies, licences, and credits
 - Relationships to other components
 - Bibliography
 - Funding body.
4. Wrapping things up.

Please visit <https://bit.ly/reeco-schema> for the reference documentation. The Permalink for this GitHub repository can be found here <https://web.archive.org/web/20240220110529/https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-annotation-schema/tree/main/schema> (archived Feb 20, 2024).

³<http://github.org/reeco-framework/reeco-annotation-schema>

2.2.1 Preliminaries: working with GitHub repositories

The REECO framework is designed according to good practices of documenting open source software and data on-site, alongside the same digital objects that are produced, shared, and managed. On GitHub, this is typically done with a so-called `README.md` file, which presents the content of the repository and provides useful information to users and developers. This file is written in a format called Markdown, which is a human readable text format supporting most common typed text formatting features of HTML⁴. Although there is consensus on the fact that there *must* be a `README.md` file at the top folder of the repository, documentation can be split up in multiple files without any naming restriction, and GitHub can be used to produce and publish full-fledged Web sites following this technique. We rely on this feature to build the Ecosystem website. An important feature of Markdown files is that they allow to include a metadata *frontmatter* including structured metadata written in the YAML syntax. We rely on this feature to embed structured annotations about ecosystem components.

2.2.2 Design structure: Containers and Components

We start from the assumption that research outputs are described from within a GitHub repository and that a Markdown file is dedicated to each one of them. Such a file will include a description of the component together with documentation and links to external sources. Crucially, the YAML frontmatter will include metadata according to the REECO annotation schema.

Here, we illustrate incrementally our approach to producing annotations. First, we introduce two notions: *components* and *containers*.

Components are defined as resources that are either used or produced by the project. Typically, a component is materialised as one digital object (or a coherent collection thereof). They are possibly stored in a repository (on GitHub) but they don't need to be, as long as there exists a Markdown file describing them in a GitHub repository.

Example To give an example we look into the musoW dataset, which is a component of type Data. It makes also a good example, as this Data set belongs to a web resource outside of GitHub. But, to be able to have it as a defined component in the Polifonia Ecosystem a GitHub repository has been created which describes the main features of this dataset. This way, it can be harvested for the Ecosystem website, and monitored.

Its metadata (**label** and content) reads as:

- **Component id** musow-dataset
- **Type** Dataset
- **Name** musoW dataset
- **Description** musoW is a Linked Open Dataset of music resources available on the web. Data are described according to Schema.org and are served online in a dedicated platform for authoring, publishing and searching.
- **Work package** WP1
- **Project** polifonia-project
- **Resource** https://github.com/polifonia-project/registry_app/releases
- **Demo** <https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/musow/>
- **Release date** 2023/05/16
- **Release** number v1.0
- **Release link** https://github.com/polifonia-project/registry_app/releases/tag/v1.0
- **DOI** 10.5281/zenodo.5603223
- **Changelog** https://github.com/polifonia-project/registry_app/releases/latest
- **Licence** CC010Universal
- **Contributors** Marilena Daquino, Enrico Daga, Albert Merono Penuela, Paul Mulholland, Simon Holland, Mathieu d'Aquin

⁴More on documenting software on GitHub: <https://docs.github.com/en/get-started>

- **Related components** Generated by: CLEF (WebApplication); Persona: Laurent (Persona); Story: Music Archives (Story)
- **Reuses** Schema.org <https://schema.org>
- **Bibliography** Main publication: Daquino, M., Wigham, M., Daga, E., Giagnoloni, L., & Tomasi, F. (2023). Clef. a linked open data native system for crowdsourcing. JOCCH. DOI: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3594721>
Publication: Daquino Marilena et al. 2017. Characterizing the Landscape of Musical Data on the Web: state of the art and challenges. In Second Workshop on Humanities in the Semantic Web - WHiSe II, 21-25 Oct 2017, Vienna, Austria.

Containers represent activities of any sort, relevant to the research. In collaborative research projects, they are typically named work packages. Other activities may include use cases, pilots, working groups or whatever may be useful to describe a human activity that produced or relied on a certain output. A container may be also a project that lead to the development and maintenance of specific components, for example, open-source communities of spin-off activities deriving from the research project.

Generally, a container groups a set of components under the same umbrella. Both containers and components are described in a Markdown file following the same annotation method (but with slightly different metadata). Containers and components are disjoint concepts, meaning that one item can only be either of the two. In addition to that, we provide a list of types for both containers and components, reusing common concepts from Schema.org, Prov-O, and other ontologies. Figures 1 and 2 provide further examples of a container and a component, respectively.

```

22 related-components:
23 - informed-by: sparql-anything-requirements
24 - documentation:
25   - sparql-anything-docs
26   - sparql-anything-tutorials
27 - extends:
28   - "Apache Jena https://jena.apache.org/"
29 - reuses:
30   - "SPARQL 1.1 Query Language https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/"

```

```

9 related-components:
10 - informed-by:
11   - sparql-anything-requirements
12   - sparql-anything-cli
13   - sparql-anything-server

```

Figure 2.1: SPARQL Anything Java source code relations **Figure 2.2:** SPARQL Anything documentation, relations

In order to select the relevant components we pursued two directions. First, we identified the main types of data sources and the main types of questions (knowledge units) in the Socio-technical roadmap. We called them the 'atlas of Polifonia' [7]. In parallel, in the initial phase, we asked developers to list the component types available already in GitHub. In addition, we posed the question of how the components are related to the project structure or if there is another project to group them (beyond what's intended in the research project, e.g. a work package). Finally, through the iterations of the Data Management Plan versions, we listed important Data, Tools, Reports and checked if they have already a repository in GitHub, if they are annotated, and so on. Thus, components and containers were determined in an iterative process.

Container and component types are listed in the Table 2.2. We identify three high-level types: Data, Tools, Reports for the navigation in the [Polifonia Ecosystem website](#). However, Tools cover a wide range of digital objects. We differentiated in particular between Software and Applications, which are executed differently (see below).

Data are digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest.

These include various types of digital objects such as datasets, corpora, ontologies, or repositories.

Tool This is any project output which is released as [Software] or [Applications].

Software is any digital object that is being produced by the project to achieve a certain task computationally.

Applications are executable systems and tools produced by the project for the end-user to achieve a certain task computationally.

Reports are any digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest. Reports differ from data as they are mainly directed to human consumption, rather than computational treatment.

Table 2.2: Container and component types

Container Type	Description	
Project	An activity grouping a set of components	
WorkingGroup	A working group	
WorkPackage	A work package	
Task	Tasks can break down work packages	
UseCase	Use cases apply and evaluate software and data outputs	
Pilot	Pilots instantiate applications into real-world scenarios	
Parent type	Component Type	Description
-	<i>Data</i>	Data represents a general type for any data resource
Data	Dataset	Dataset specify a data objects focused on collecting facts about a given observation/population
Data	Schema	Schemas specify data structures
Data	Repository	Repositories stores digital objects
Dataset	Registry	Registries are datasets focusing on the indexing of resources
Dataset	Ontology	Ontology
Dataset	Corpus	Corpus
Dataset	Lexicon	Lexicon
Dataset	KnowledgeGraph	Knowledge Graph
-	<i>Tools – Software</i>	A general term for specifying source code or executable digital objects
Software	Workflow	Workflows are declarative, sometimes executable specifications of complex automations
Software	API	API
Software	UserInterface	User interface
Software	DockerImageContainer	Docker Image Container
Software	SoftwareLibrary	Software Library
Software	Notebook	Notebook
Software	Script	Script
-	<i>Tools –Application</i>	Application
Application	WebSite	Web site
Application	WebApplication	WebApplication
Application	WebService	Web Service
WebService	SPARQLEndpoint	SPARQL Endpoint
Web site	EcosystemWebsite	Ecosystem Website
Application	MobileApp	Mobile application
Application	CLITool	Command Line Interface Tool
-	<i>Report</i>	Report
Report	Survey	Survey
Survey	InPresenceSurvey	In presence survey
Survey	FocusGroup	Focus Group
Report	RequirementsCollection	Requirements Collection
RequirementsCollection	Story	Story
RequirementsCollection	Persona	Persona
RequirementsCollection	Mockup	Mockup
Report	Deliverable	Deliverable
Report	Documentation	Documentation
Documentation	Tutorial	Tutorial
Report	EvaluationReport	Evaluation Report

Furthermore, we provide the following questions and recommendations:

- *How many components?* A repository may include one or more items of interest. The ecosystem considers four main types of components: Data, Software, Application, and Report.
- *Is there a container?* If there is an umbrella project/activity beyond the structure of the research project, it may be useful to define a container. For example, a software project may include different things, source code, specifications, documentations, tutorials, multiple runnable artifacts, and so forth.
- Annotators **MUST** include a '.md' file for each one of them
- Repositories **COULD** expose more than one component
- Components **SHOULD NOT** be associated with more than one container
- Annotators **MAY** reuse the main repository README .md file.
- Annotators **MAY** describe resources that are not managed in the repository, by creating specific Markdown files for each one of them. This may be useful if they want to reference an existing work that has an independent development life-cycle.
- Annotators **MAY** group all Markdown files in a folder named 'ecosystem'.

For example, SPARQL Anything is an open source software project that was initiated by the EU-funded project SPICE⁵ and is being applied and extended in Polifonia. Therefore, it is part of the Polifonia ecosystem. However, it is built and maintained in a collection of repositories under the sparql-anything organisation. We decide to describe it as a collection of components under an umbrella project. In the case of SPARQL Anything, we make the following design decisions:

- SPARQL Anything (Project) → Container!
- Java Source Code (Software)
- Python Library (SoftwareLibrary)
- Command line interface (CLITool)
- Fuseki Server (WebApplication)
- Online documentation (Documentation)
- Docker container (DockerImageContainer)
- A list of tutorials (Tutorial)
- Requirements (RequirementsCollection)

We create a Markdown file for each one of them, as illustrated in Figure 2.3. Overall, we ask users to achieve a balance between the core top component types: Data, Software, Application, and Documentation.

Figure 2.3: SPARQL Anything ecosystem components

2.2.3 Identifier, type, and descriptive metadata

At this stage, we have one or more Markdown files representing containers and components. We proceed including an identifier, a type, and descriptive metadata. The metadata schema elements are illustrated in Table 2.3. Figure 2.4 shows annotations for the main container of the SPARQL Anything project, while Figure 2.5 shows the annotations for the Command Line Interface component. In addition, we recommend providing an extended description and documentation in the body of the Markdown, with a header including the name of the component (or container).

⁵SPICE: Social cohesion, Participation, and Inclusion through Cultural Engagement, DOI: DOI 10.3030/870811 <http://spice-h2020.eu>

Term	Description
component-id	The ID of the component in the Ecosystem. Can be a local identifier or a URI.
container-id	The ID of the container in the Ecosystem. Can be a local identifier or a URI.
type	The component/container type, according to the list of component types. NOTE: Only one value is allowed.
name	The name of the component/container
description	A text describing the component/container
image	Link to one reference image illustrating the component/container
logo	Logo of the component in Web format. Accepted image formats are JPEG and PNG.
demo (components only)	Link to an online demo of the component
work-package	The <code>container-id</code> of all work packages relevant to the component or container (e.g. WP1, WP2,...)
pilot	The <code>container-id</code> of all work packages relevant to the component or container (e.g. from Polifonia: MEETUPS, CHILD, INTERLINK ...)

Table 2.3: List of identifier and descriptive metadata

```

container-id: sparql-anything
name: SPARQL Anything
description: SPARQL Anything is a system for Semantic Web re-engineering that allows to query non-RDF files as-if they were RDF.
type: Project
work-package:
- WP1
- WP2
pilot:
- MEETUPS
- INTERLINK
project: polifonia-project

```

Figure 2.4: SPARQL Anything container

```

component-id: sparql-anything-cli
type: CLITool
name: SPARQL Anything Command Line
description: Command line executable of SPARQL Anything
logo: https://avatars.githubusercontent.com/u/79987779?s=200&v=4
work-package:
- WP1
- WP2
- WP3
- WP4
pilot:
- MEETUPS
- CHILD
project: polifonia-project

```

Figure 2.5: SPARQL Anything Command Line Interface component

2.2.4 Resources, releases, and DOIs (components only)

At this stage of the process, a collection of Markdown files include basic descriptive metadata. We proceed producing a first set of annotations, focusing on resources, releases and other identifiers such as DOI. These are listed in Table 2.4. These terms are required for components only. Figure 2.6 shows annotations for the SPARQL Anything Command Line Interface.

Term	Description
resource	The digital resource represented by the component (e.g. if the component is of type Dataset, it may point to a file or a folder in the repository). Values can be the path to a file (if 1 file), the path to a folder (if many files), or the absolute URL of an online file (DOIs should not be used here).
demo	Link to an online demo of the component
release-date	The date the component was released. Accepted values include any valid XSD date.
release-number	Version number of the release. Any value is permitted, although we recommend semantic versioning: https://semver.org/
release-link	Link to access or download the component release
doi	The DOI of the GitHub repository related to this component, e.g. as published on Zenodo.org
changelog	Link to a Changelog document, a file which contains a chronologically ordered list of notable changes for each version of the component.

Table 2.4: Terms for resources, releases, and DOI

```

16 resource: https://github.com/SPARQL-Anything/sparql.anything/releases
17 demo: https://github.com/SPARQL-Anything/showcase-tate
18 release-date: 2022/12/18
19 release-number: v0.8.1
20 release-link: https://github.com/SPARQL-Anything/sparql.anything/releases/tag/v0.8.1
21 doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7454360
22 changelog: https://github.com/SPARQL-Anything/sparql.anything/releases/tag/v0.8.1

```

Figure 2.6: Resources, release, and DOI for the SPARQL Anything Command Line Interface component

```

23 licence:
24 - Apache-2.0
25 copyright: "Copyright (c) 2022 SPARQL Anything Contributors @ http://github.com/sparql-anything"
26 contributors:
27 - Luigi Asprino <https://github.com/luigi-asprino>
28 - Enrico Daga <https://github.com/enridaga>
29 - Justin Dowdy <https://github.com/justin2004>
30 - Marco Ratta <https://github.com/MarcoR1791>

```

Figure 2.7: Licence, copyright, and credit information for SPARQL Anything components

2.2.5 Policies, licensing, and credits (components only)

The next set of descriptors relate to licencing and copyright information, and credit (see Table 2.5). Credits list all contributors to the component, while copyright captures information on ownership and attribution. Licences have special treatment in the ecosystem annotations schema. We leverage recent advances in computational representation of terms of use by relying on Semantic Web technologies, specifically, the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) and the Dalicc⁶ catalogue of licences expressed in RDF/ODRL [9]. Further information can be found in deliverable D2.6 [10]. The annotation schema provides a list of supported licence codes that can be used as values in the metadata⁷. An example is shown in Figure 2.7.

Table 2.5: Licencing, credits, and copyright information

Term	Description
licence	A list of codes pointing to supported licences in the framework (or a link to a licence document).
copyright	Copyright information
contributors	A list of contributors in the form: "Name <name.surname@mail.com>"

⁶<http://www.dalicc.net>

⁷See <https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-annotation-schema/tree/main/schema#licences>

Table 2.6: Relations to other components.

Term	Description
related-components	List of components that are related to this one.
informed-by	The component was informed by another component (or resource), for example, a requirements document or a Persona, a Story, a use case, etc...
use-case	Link to one or more use cases. This term is a specialisation of 'informed-by'
story	Link to one or more user stories. This term is a specialisation of 'informed-by'.
persona	Link to one or more persona. This term is a specialisation of 'informed-by'.
documentation	Link to the documentation of the component.
evaluated-in	Link to a document (e.g. a user study) or source code demonstrating the validity of the component.
extends	Link to a component that is extended by the current component. If not a component, can be an external URI
reuses	Link to a component that is reused as-is by the current component. Can be a component or an external URL.
serves	Link to a dataset that is served by the current component (e.g. an API). Can be a component or an external dataset.
generated-by	Link to a software, dataset, or any other component that produced or generated the current component. Can be a component or an external URL.
derived-from	Link to a resource from which this component was derived.

2.2.7 Bibliography

The bibliography section allows to annotate components with articles, technical reports, and other related publications. We include two single-valued terms for annotating the items with the principal related work: `main-publication` and `main-report` to link a peer reviewed publication or a non-peer reviewed one, respectively. Other terms are allowed to extend the bibliography associated with the item. These annotations are available for both components and containers, with the exception of `published-in` that is directed to link components, mainly software or data, to a reference resource description publication. The terms are listed and described in Table 2.7 and example annotations are shown in Figure 2.10.

Table 2.7: Bibliography annotations for components and containers

Term	Description
bibliography	A section grouping bibliographic references that are relevant to the component but that do not fall under a specific category. The following terms appear under this section. Use "main-publication" for the main scholarly publication related to the component
published-in (components only)	Link to a meaningful venue where the current component is served or published (e.g. a dataset published on a web portal).
main-publication	The primary, peer-reviewed scientific publication related to this component (if non peer-reviewed, use main-report instead).
publication	A peer reviewed scientific publication related to this component (if non peer-reviewed, use report instead).
main-report	The primary document related to this component (if peer-reviewed publication, use main-publication instead).
report	A document related to this component (if peer-reviewed publication, use publication instead).
deliverable-document	Link to the deliverable document related to this component.

```

31 related-components:
32 - informed-by: sparql-anything-requirements
33 - documentation:
34 - sparql-anything-docs
35 - sparql-anything-tutorials
36 - reuses:
37 - sparql-anything-java

```

Figure 2.9: SPARQL Anything CLI relations

```

14 bibliography:
15 - main-publication: "Asprino, Luigi, Enrico Daga, Aldo Gangemi, and Paul Mulholland. \"
16   façade: a unified method to access heterogeneous data sources on the Web.\" ACM Transac
17   (2023): 1-31. https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3555312"
18 - publication:
19   - "Daga, Enrico, Luigi Asprino, Paul Mulholland, and Aldo Gangemi. \"Facade-X: an opi
20     anything.\" Studies on the Semantic Web 53 (2021): 58-73."
21   - "Ratta, Marco, and Enrico Daga. \"Knowledge Graph Construction From MusicXML\": An
22     Anything. http://oro.open.ac.uk/85326/1/Music_Knowledge_Graphs_Paper%20%281%29.pdf"

```

Figure 2.10: Bibliography information

2.2.8 Funding body (containers only)

Activities can report details of the funding body (Table 2.8). Activities can be linked to one or more funding bodies. The terms allow to specify three aspects: the name of the funder, a link to a Web site, and a reference identifier for the grant agreement. Funding details are shown in Figure 2.11.

Table 2.8: Funding bodies

funder	The section lists all funding bodies of the project (the following data terms apply to each one of them).
funder/name	The name of the funding programme
funder/url	Link to the funder organisation web site
funder/grant-agreement	Identifier of the grant agreement relative to the funding organisation

```

19 - funder:
20   - name: European Commission H2020
21     url: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/h2020
22     grant-agreement: "GA101004746"
23 credits: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under
24   grant agreement GA101004746. The communication reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not
25   responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains."
26 - has-part:

```

Figure 2.11: Funding body details

2.2.9 Wrapping things up

Finally, containers should include links to all relevant components using the term `has-part`. An example is illustrated in Figure 2.12.

As a final step, a number of actions are recommended:

1. Configure the GitHub integration with Zenodo, following the official documentation⁸.
2. Generate an initial release of the repository via GitHub. This action will trigger the Zenodo integration. The repository content will be published on Zenodo, and a DOI generated. Users can further enhance annotations including the DOI on each one of the items in the repository.

⁸Instructions at <https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/archiving-a-github-repository/referencing-and-citing-content>

```

1 ---
2 container-id: sparql-anything
3 name: SPARQL Anything
4 description: SPARQL Anything is a system for Semantic Web re-engineering that allows to query non-RDF files as-if they are in
5 RDF.
6 type: Project
7 work-package:
8   - WP1
9   - WP2
10  - WP4
11 pilot:
12   - MEETUPS
13   - CHILD
14 project: polifonia-project
15 bibliography:
16   - main-publication: "Asprino, Luigi, Enrico Daga, Aldo Gangemi, and Paul Mulholland. \"Knowledge Graph Construction with a
17     facade: a unified method to access heterogeneous data sources on the Web.\" ACM Transactions on Internet Technology 23, no. 1
18     (2023): 1-31. https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3555312"
19   - publication:
20     - "Daga, Enrico, Luigi Asprino, Paul Mulholland, and Aldo Gangemi. \"Facade-X: an opinionated approach to SPARQL
21       anything.\" Studies on the Semantic Web 53 (2021): 58-73."
22     - "Ratta, Marco, and Enrico Daga. \"Knowledge Graph Construction From MusicXML\": An Empirical Investigation With SPARQL
23       Anything. http://oro.open.ac.uk/85326/1/Music\_Knowledge\_Graphs\_Paper%20%281%29.pdf"
24   - funder:
25     - name: European Commission H2020
26     url: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/h2020
27     grant-agreement: "GA101004746"
28     - name: European Commission H2020
29     url: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/h2020
30     grant-agreement: "GA870811"
31 credits: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under
32 grant agreements GA101004746 (Polifonia) and GA870811 (SPICE)."
33 has-part:
34   - sparql-anything-cli
35   - sparql-anything-java
36   - sparql-anything-docs
37   - sparql-anything-tutorials
38   - sparql-anything-python
39   - sparql-anything-requirements
40   - sparql-anything-docker
41 ---
    
```

Figure 2.12: Full example of annotated container

2.3 The REECO annotations validator - tool support

In the previous section we introduced the Reeco annotation schema and described a step-by-step process for producing meaningful and rich annotations. However, such activity requires attention to detail and it can be easy to make mistakes or overlook existing errors. For this reason, we developed a system to support users in validating annotations. The REECO Web Repo Validator⁹ scans the content of a given repository input for ecosystem annotated Markdown files (either components or containers) and validates the annotations against a set of pre-defined rules. These are listed in Table 2.9. The tool allows users to input the path of a public GitHub repository, specifying the branch or tag they want to validate (Figure 2.13). On submission, the tool validates the repository against the pre-defined rules. The output of the process is presented in Figure 2.14. The validator shows a list of Markdown files found in the repository. Users can review the annotations available and a validation report is provided for each one of them as a list of messages:

- An error message is displayed for any missing mandatory term or violated value constraint (for example, a component id including a space or a non-resolvable release URL).
- A warning message is shown for any missing recommended field. For example, a missing bibliography reference.
- An information message is displayed if the tool could not find any annotation on the Markdown file (the file was not a component or neither component-id nor container-id were included in the YAML front-matter).

⁹<https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-web-repo-validator>

Finally, each message includes a direct link to the file on GitHub, so that users can easily access the annotated file, and edit the data to fix errors or integrate new information. Users can change the content directly on GitHub and refresh the validator browser's page to see updated messages, therefore, incrementally curating and improving the annotations until no further change is required.

Reeco Annotations Validator

Enter GitHub repository URL

GitHub repository URL

Tree (defaults to "main")

Figure 2.13: Annotations validator input

Repository

<https://github.com/polifonia-project/patterns-knowledge-graph> (main) 4 files found.

List of files:

[P2KG-Pipeline/readme.md](#)

[README.md](#)

[patterns-knowledge-graph-datasets/README.md](#)

[queries/README.md](#)

Validation report

[P2KG-Pipeline/readme.md](#)

Key 'demo' error: URL cannot be resolved. File: [P2KG-Pipeline/readme.md](#)

[README.md](#)

No errors found.

Key 'funder' error: The activity should have at least one funding organisation. File: [README.md](#)

[patterns-knowledge-graph-datasets/README.md](#)

Key 'demo' error: URL cannot be resolved. File: [patterns-knowledge-graph-datasets/README.md](#)

[queries/README.md](#)

Not a component: no annotations found File: [queries/README.md](#)

Figure 2.14: Annotations validator report

Table 2.9: List of validation rules. The policy column indicates if the term is mandatory (M), recommended (R), or optional (O). The Constraints column reports additional restrictions.

Term	Data type	Policy	Constraints
<i>Containers</i>			
container-id	Str	M	Incompatible with component-id. Must respect the regular expression: $[\^s]+(/[\^s]+(/[\^s]+)?)?$
name	Str	M	
description	Str	M	
type	Str	M	Must be one of the supported container types (Table 2.2)
funder	List	R	Must be a list of structured items (recommended at least one).
- name	Str	M	If a funder is specified, the name is mandatory
- url	Str	M	If a funder is specified, the URL needs to be a <i>valid</i> and <i>resolvable</i> HTTP URL.
- grant-agreement	Str	O	If a funder is specified, a grant-agreement number can be also added.
has-part	List	M	A list of component ids that result from this activity. At least one component needs to be mentioned.
<i>Components</i>			
component-id	Str	M	Incompatible with container-id. Must respect the regular expression: $[\^s]+(/[\^s]+(/[\^s]+)?)?$
name	Str	M	
description	Str	M	
resource	Str	O	
doi	Str	O	Should respect one of the following regular expressions: (a) $^10.\d{4,9}/[-._;()/:A-Z0-9]+$ (b) $^10.1002/[\^s]+$ (c) $^10.\d{4}/\d+-\d+X?(\d+)\d+<[\d\w]+:[\d\w]*>\d+.\d+.\w+;\d$
release-date	Str	O	
release-number	Str	O	
release-link	Str	O	Must be a valid and resolvable URL
changelog	Str	O	
licence	List	M	Licence must be a list of licence codes from the Reeco Annotation Schema reference. At least one licence must be included.
image	Str	O	Must be a valid and resolvable URL
logo	Str	O	Must be a valid and resolvable URL
demo	Str	O	Must be a valid and resolvable URL
running-instance	Str	O	Must be a valid and resolvable URL
contributors	List	O	
related-components	List	M	At least another component needs to be referenced with one of the allowed sub-terms (see Table 2.6).
bibliography	List	R	It is recommended to include bibliographic information with at least one of the allowed sub-terms (see Table 2.7).
work-package	Str	O	A valid component-id. Must respect the regular expression: $[\^s]+(/[\^s]+(/[\^s]+)?)?$
pilot	Str	O	A valid component-id. Must respect the regular expression: $[\^s]+(/[\^s]+(/[\^s]+)?)?$
project	Str	O	A valid container-id. Must respect the regular expression: $[\^s]+(/[\^s]+(/[\^s]+)?)?$

2.4 The REECO ecosystem website builder: Building and publishing Research Ecosystems

In this section we describe how we use the annotation schema to collect and build a research ecosystem, a structured knowledge graph of activities and outputs of collaborative research projects.

The Research Ecosystem Website is the main output and access point to the research ecosystem.

The website relies on the Github action feature, which allows to trigger automatic operations on specific repository events. For example, we use the standard GitHub pages action to build and publish a static website directly from a GitHub repository. The facility relies on the Jekyll template engine. However, the goal of the Ecosystem website is to collect and publish metadata about the research activities and components. Therefore, we extend the Jekyll engine and GitHub pages method by providing a custom action, which is triggered at any change in the repository.

Figure 2.15: REECO custom Github action workflow

Overall, the process to initialise and configure the Research Ecosystem Website is as follows, which we expand in the following subsections:

1. Fork the REECO Jekyll template project, which already include the Github action and example content.
2. Customise the list of repositories to include (file `repositories.txt`).
3. Commit changes and trigger the REECO GitHub action (described in Figure 2.15).
4. Configure the content of the Jekyll config file.
5. Personalise the website, curate static content (work packages, pilots, and main page) and look and feel.

2.4.1 Fork the REECO Jekyll template project

Users can setup their own ecosystem website by copying (or forking¹⁰) the content of the template project <http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-jekyll>. Users can rename the project as they prefer.

2.4.2 Customise repositories.txt

The file `repositories.txt` lists the repositories that include component annotations that need to be collected and integrated in the research ecosystem. Users should provide the full name of the repository, as well as the related branch or release tag to be used. An example of the content of `repositories.txt` can be seen in Figure 2.16.

¹⁰See <https://docs.github.com/en/pull-requests/collaborating-with-pull-requests/working-with-forks/fork-a-repo>

```
reeco-framework/reeco-annotation-schema:branches:main
reeco-framework/reeco-website-action:branches:main
reeco-framework/reeco-web-repo-validator:branches:main
reeco-framework/reeco-python:branches:main
reeco-framework/reeco-documentation:branches:main
```

Figure 2.16: Example content of the `repositories.txt` configuration file. Each line includes a repository path (including the organisation), whether the content is in ‘branches’ or ‘tag’ and the name of the branch or tag. Values are separated by the ‘:’ character. In this example, all repositories are checked out from the main branch.

2.4.3 Commit changes and trigger the REECO Github action

When the user commits the changes, the custom action is triggered and the system executes the following workflow (also illustrated in Figure 2.15):

- initialize reeco The first step is to check if the `repositories.txt` file is present. If not, the workflow opens an issue with basic instructions for configuration.
- fetch components If the configuration file exists, the system downloads all the Markdown files from the linked repositories
- validate yml Files are validated according to the annotation schema validation rules (see Table 2.9). Error messages are saved into a validation report for future use into a data file within the ecosystem website project.
- check zenodo The zenodo API is invoked to verify the repositories are released and deposited. Next, annotations are checked for DOIs. In the case components include a DOI, citation details are fetched in different styles and stored in a data file within the ecosystem website project. This last step is performed with the support of a SPARQL Anything query, reported in Figure 2.18.
- generate RDF Component annotations are transformed into RDF data. We apply a SPARQL Anything [12] query to construct RDF graphs directly from the Markdown annotations. Figure 2.19 illustrates the annotations expressed as Schema.org¹¹. The output of this process are a collections of Schema.org annotations in JSON-LD format. Such annotations are then embedded in each component page on the website.
- build site The generated content is saved into the repository and the GitHub pages action is triggered, which in turn builds and deploy the website.

Users can perform changes to the `repositories.txt` incrementally and see the result generated on each change.

2.4.4 Configure the content of the Jekyll config file.

The main configuration file of Jekyll is `config.yml`¹². Users can follow the Jekyll documentation as a guidelines. A few configuration options are specific to the REECO template. Users can customise the base namespace for the RDF entities generated as follows:

```
rdf:
  namespace: "https://reeco-framework.github.io/ecosystem/entity/"
```

Validation messages can be displayed as part of the component page metadata, to help troubleshooting:

```
reeco:
  validate: true
```

¹¹The query can be inspected at <https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-website-action/blob/main/components-to-rdf.sparql>

¹²See also <https://jekyllrb.com/docs/configuration/>

Repository organisations listed in the `repositories.txt` file are included as Jekyll collections, and in the just-the-docs template configuration, to allow indexing enabling the Search feature.

```
collections:
  reeco-framework:
    output: true
defaults:
  - scope:
      type: reeco-framework
    values:
      layout: component
[...]
just_the_docs:
  search_enabled: true
  [...]
collections:
  reeco-framework:
    name: reeco-framework
    nav_exclude: true
    search_exclude: false
```

2.4.5 Personalise the website

Finally, users can curate static content of the website, for example, generating pages for work packages, pilots, changing the content of the main page and producing their own look and feel.

The REECO Website template provides a number of features to navigate and explore ecosystem components:

1. means to browse, search, and explore activities and components
2. overview and statistics of component types, organised in three high-level categories: data, tools (software and applications), and reports
3. overview of components organised by licences
4. embedded metadata with Schema.org
5. ability to export the data as a knowledge graph.

A demo website can be seen at <http://reeco-framework.github.io/reeco-jekyll>. Figure 2.17 shows the home page and look and feel. A complete demonstrator of the REECO framework is the Polifonia Ecosystem, published at <http://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem>, whose content was described in D7.2 [3].

Figure 2.17: Research Ecosystem Website front page. The image illustrates the appearance of the website template, populated with exemplary components from the REECO project. The example website is live at <http://reeco-framework.github.io/reeco-jekyll>

```

PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX fx: <http://sparql.xyz/facade-x/ns/>
PREFIX xyz: <http://sparql.xyz/facade-x/data/>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX schema: <https://schema.org/>
PREFIX fabio: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/>
PREFIX frapo: <http://purl.org/cerif/frapo/>

SELECT ?component ?doi ?apa ?bibtex
WHERE {

    SERVICE <x-sparql-anything:> {

        SERVICE <x-sparql-anything:> {

            # --> Step 1. extract the YAML fontmatter from files with component
            # annotations
            fx:properties fx:location ?_componentFile .
            [] a xyz:YamlFrontMatter ; fx:anySlot ?yaml
        }

        BIND ( ?yaml as ?content ) .

        #--> Step 2. parse the YAML content
        fx:properties fx:content ?content ;
        fx:triplifier "io.github.sparqlanything.yaml.YAMLTriplifier" ; fx:blank-
        nodes "false" ; fx:yaml.allow-duplicate-keys true.

        { # Components:
          # Id
          ?x xyz:component-id ?component .
          ?x xyz:doi ?doi .
        }
    }
    ### curl -LH "Accept: text/x-bibliography; style=apa" https://doi.org/10.1126/science
    .169.3946.635

    BIND ( IF(fx:String.startsWith(?doi, "http"), ?doi, CONCAT("https://doi.org/", ?doi)) AS
    ?doiLink ) .
    OPTIONAL{
    SERVICE SILENT <x-sparql-anything:> {

    fx:properties fx:location ?doiLink ;
    fx:http.header.accept "text/x-bibliography; style=apa" ;
    fx:media-type "text/plain" .
    [] rdf:_1 ?apa
    }}
    OPTIONAL{
    SERVICE SILENT <x-sparql-anything:> {
    fx:properties fx:location ?doiLink ;
    fx:http.header.accept "text/x-bibliography; style=bibtex" ;
    fx:media-type "text/plain" .
    [] rdf:_1 ?bibtex
    }
    }
}
}

```

Figure 2.18: SPARQL Anything query to fetch citation information in APA and Bibtex, following DOIs in YAML annotations from component files in Markdown.

Figure 2.19: Schema.org metadata generated from components' annotations

3 The Polifonia Ecosystem - an implementation of the REECO

Figure 3.1: Polifonia Ecosystem Website

In this section, we present the Polifonia Ecosystem as an example of how the REECO framework can be applied to a rich, complex collaborative research project. We have extensively elaborated on the Polifonia approach to research data management in other deliverables (D1.3 [13], D7.1 [2], D7.3 [4]), and in those documents (in particular in the last version of the Data Management Plan (D7.3 [4]) we describe how to build and navigate the structure of the Polifonia Ecosystem. In this chapter, we show the Polifonia Ecosystem website to illustrate how a REECO-powered ecosystem instance looks like. We do this in essence by providing a series of snapshots illustrating the main features. We invite the reader to visit and explore the website of the [Polifonia Ecosystem](#) themselves.

The Polifonia Ecosystem includes more than 100 components. The main page shows a summary of component types and statistics. Components are organised first by Work Package (Figure 3.2 shows WP1) and Pilots (Figure 3.3 shows the BELLS pilot page).

Users can choose to develop more views than the ones provided by the REECO template. For example, in Polifonia, we created a view of requirements (aka Stories) that played an important role in scoping the objectives of the project (see Figure 3.4). A licences page allows to explore the components by their licence requirements (Figure 3.5).

Dedicated sections group components under three macro-categories: Data (Figures 3.6 and 3.7), Tools (including components of type Software and Application) and Report.

A general search feature allow to perform text-based searches on the whole content (see Figure 3.8 for an example of a user searching for "Organ"). The result set allows a snippet of the content matching the search with link to the related page.

Each component page include the full set of metadata, with facilities to support users in how to cite the content and downloaded Schema.org JSON-LD annotations. Furthermore, the whole ecosystem dataset is published for

Figure 3.2: The Work Package page lists all components relevant to the WP.

Figure 3.3: The Work Package page lists all components relevant to the WP.

Figure 3.4: Polifonia stories

Figure 3.5: Polifonia ecosystem components, organised by licence

download and reuse¹. Component pages displaying metadata provide links to other, related components, which can be also followed.

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/ecosystem/blob/main/ecosystem.nt>

Figure 3.6: Overview of components of type data (top of the page)

Figure 3.7: Overview of components of type data (continued)

Figure 3.8: Example of the search feature on the Polifonia Ecosystem Website

Figure 3.9: Polifonia Component Metadata (BELLS Ontology)

Figure 3.10: Polifonia Component Metadata (MEETUPS Time Extraction)

4 Citing other scholarly objects in Polifonia

In this chapter, we survey a selection of Polifonia tools that support the citation of different musical scholarly data, tailored to specialised user domains.

4.1 MELODY

Make me a Linked Open Data storY (MELODY)¹ is a web platform where scholars of Polifonia and external users can create and publish web-ready article-like **data stories**. Data stories are web documents wherein text content is alternated with charts, graphs, and maps, built on top of a Linked Open Data source (see for example the story called *Discover music data on the web*², built on top of musoW data³, also shown in Fig. 4.1). Authors of a story can modify the order of visual components in the page via a user-friendly backend interface. MELODY is described in D1.9 [14] and D1.10. Data stories created on MELODY by Polifonia partners are published on the same platform and are accessible via the left-side menu. Stories created by external users are published (free-of-charge) on an external venue⁴. Each data story is identified by a URL and the metadata that authors include as part of the story (e.g. title, authors, provenance of data used to create charts). A story can be exported in several formats, i.e. HTML documents (to be published somewhere else), PDF documents, or JSON files (which includes the sequence of text content and SPARQL queries to reproduce charts in a different context). Similarly, each graphic component of a data story can be exported for reuse as an image, an HTML snippet to be embedded in another web page, and as a SPARQL query (Fig. 4.2).

Figure 4.1: An example of data story on MELODY. The story can be cited and exported in several formats

¹<https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody>

²https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/musow/discover_music_data_on_the_web

³<https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/musow/>

⁴<https://melody-data.github.io/stories/>

Figure 4.2: An example of chart on MELODY. The chart can be exported in several formats

4.2 Web portal

The Polifonia Web portal⁵ is the main gateway to Polifonia data. The portal leverages data belonging to several datasets (both internal and external to the Polifonia project) and offers user-friendly interfaces for serendipitous knowledge discovery. It is designed to support lay users in the exploration of the European music heritage. The Web portal is described in D1.9 [14] and D1.10.

In particular, users of the web portal can search across all indexed datasets (described here⁶) and retrieve descriptive web pages for the most **important entities**, such as artists, music works, places, and instruments (see an example of entity in Fig. 4.3). While entities can be cited via their persistent URIs (minted and maintained by data providers), web pages of entities can be cited via their URL and can be easily shared on other platforms thanks to share buttons (see Fig. 4.3). When the entity at hand appears in several datasets (hence it would be identified by multiple URIs), a new URI is minted, e.g. https://w3id.org/polifonia/linkset/d_04__d_01__cat_02__389afd8d-fc9d-4479-afdd-882996b77cc3. Such a new URI is stored in a dedicated linkset, i.e. a named graph stored on the Polifonia central triplestore, and it is linked to all the URIs representing the same entity in data sources.

Figure 4.3: An example of an entity in the Web portal and how to cite the web page

⁵<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/portal>

⁶<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/portal/about>

4.3 PON / Interlink

The INTERLINK pilot aims at connecting KGs of European musical cultural heritage, which are notoriously large and use a diversified vocabulary of relations. The pilot is not bound to specific institutional datasets, collections or use cases; but rather summarises the common needs of all pilots of representing their data as music knowledge graphs, and develops methodologies that enable finding new meaningful connections among them.

To achieve this vision, INTERLINK has joined efforts with WP2 to integrate the requirements of all pilots and contribute ontologies for the interoperability of music data. This led to the development of the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) [15]. Of particular interest to INTERLINK is the semantic representation of **music metadata** (alias bibliographic, or documentary music data) it is used to consistently identify and describe musical works, their artists, recordings, and performances. Music metadata allows for efficient management and distribution of music, which facilitates search and recommendation [16]; and its accuracy contributes to ensuring proper credit and compensation to artists [17].

A central contribution here is the Music Meta ontology in PON [18] – a rich and flexible semantic model for (Western) music metadata across different genres and periods. The model abstracts from the specificity of a particular genre, allowing to reduce complexity while maintaining alignment to other ontologies (Music Ontology [19], DOREMUS [20]); and also accounts for provenance, which is necessary when integrating different sources.

The ability to semantically represent music metadata in a consistent way, either directly (direct reuse of Music Meta) or indirectly (e.g. ontology alignment) is a fundamental step for the interlinking of Music KGs. An example of this is ChoCo [21], a musical harmony KG that integrates 18 different datasets using Music Meta; and its reuse for harmonic similarity and pattern discovery [22]. Through semantic interoperability, music resources are described via the same concepts and relation types, which facilitate information retrieval and knowledge discovery – including linking. While contributing to consistently citing and annotating music scholarly objects, the reuse of PON/Meta is thus a requirement for the integration of musical resources via the methodologies developed in INTERLINK [23, 24].

4.4 Meetups

At the core of the MEETUPS pilot is the Musical Meetups Knowledge Graph (MMKG)[25, 26], describing the intersections of historical figures in music in the form of meetup events [27, 28]. These events are categorised by a number of attributes including location, time, theme and the participants involved. By combining the MMKG with a web-based user interface, we provide a platform that enables users to delve into a broad exploratory analysis of historical narratives, uncovering patterns and behaviours embedded within the lives of these figures.

The web tool's design facilitates a multifaceted approach to data exploration, offering a range of visualisations and perspectives. This flexibility results in a dynamic interface capable of adopting numerous states, tailored to the exploratory journey of the user. It is crucial, therefore, that the tool allows for the documentation of this exploration journey in a manner that is both easily replicable and personal, enabling users to revisit their unique pathways at any time or share these pathways in the form of a citable reference.

The MEETUPS application is structured around two principal web pages: the biography page, which allows users to investigate all data pertaining to a single figure, and the explore page, which provides the freedom to search for meetups using various criteria. Each page is equipped with multiple view options, including:

- Alternate data presentations accessible through different tabs
- An interactive map for geographical exploration, which users can pan and zoom
- A details panel that displays comprehensive attributes of a selected meetup

Significantly, adjusting these views does not necessitate a page reload. Instead, view changes are seamlessly integrated into the application's URL via event triggers that continuously monitor the state of the tool. These view parameters are encoded in a string, separated by '/' characters and appended after the '#' symbol in the URL, akin to a page anchor.

An example of a citable URL for Edward Elgar's biography and MMKG data, with the view specifically configured to display his meetups on a map, with the map viewport set to display the United Kingdom and Northern Europe and the details panel set to display a specific meetup with Julius Buths would be as follows:

https://polifonia.kmi.open.ac.uk/meetups/biography.php?id=http://dbpedia.org/resource/Edward_Elgar#map-tab/41.71,-28.04,58.4,30.72/2/

Figure 4.4: Examples of alternate data views within the MEETUPS application

The search and exploration page of the application follows a similar pattern of encoding the view state of the interface, while additionally capturing the specific fields and values utilised in data searches. Since searching is done via JavaScript AJAX calls to the SPARQL endpoint without a page reload, these parameters are not encoded as traditional URL parameters in the common `?param=value` style. Instead, they are added to the view-state string following the '#' symbol alongside the other view parameters mentioned previously. This ensures a fluid and dynamic user experience without workflow being interrupted by page reloads.

All pages within the MEETUPS application contain a button in the footer of the page that automatically copies the current page reference to the clipboard, streamlining the process of sharing or saving citable references for users.

Figure 4.5: A button is provided on every page for capturing the current UI state as a unique reference

4.5 Patterns Knowledge Graph

The *Patterns Knowledge Graph* is a KG containing information on musical patterns, focusing especially on melodic patterns in folk music. It takes advantage of the underlying TUNES KG for metadata. It is described in Polifonia deliverables D3.3 and D3.4. Moreover, the Patterns User Interface is a UI for interaction with and exploration of musical patterns, using the Patterns KG as a backend. The Patterns UI is described in Polifonia deliverable D5.6. Specific patterns, tunes, and interaction views can be cited by taking advantage of URL structure in the Patterns UI, as follows. (We use `localhost` as a placeholder for the domain name where the UI is hosted.)

Title search <http://localhost:8080/?searchType=title&searchTerm=Lord>

Pattern search <http://localhost:8080/?searchType=pattern&searchTerm=1,+1,+1,+1>

Advanced search <http://localhost:8080/?searchType=advanced&pattern=2,+3,+1,+5&title=Lord&corpus=The+Session&key=Gmajor&timeSignature=4/4&timeSignature=2/4&tuneType=reel>

Composition page <http://localhost:8080/composition/thesession20211212%2FMusicEntity%2F13430>

Composition Page with pattern comparison to previously selected composition <http://localhost:8080/composition/thesession20211212%2FMusicEntity%2F1029/thesession20211212%2FMusicEntity%2F13430/Lord%20McDonald's>

Tune family page <http://localhost:8080/family/Lord%20McDonald's>

Pattern page <http://localhost:8080/pattern/2,%203,%201,%205,%203>

4.6 Tonalities

Tonalities' interface (<https://data-iremus.huma-num.fr/tonalities/>) has been developed with the specific aim of enabling collaborative annotation of musical scores encoded in MEI. Any element at any level of granularity – single notes, groups of notes, verticalities, whole scores – can be selected. These selections can group adjacent or non-adjacent elements and are recursive: a parent selection can contain one or more child selections, which in turn can contain selections, etc.

Selections can be associated with free user comments, which in turn may lead to comments from other users. On the other hand, selections are associated with analytical and theoretical concepts formally defined in ontologies. These models can be freely selected and are specific: analysis of the fugue, analysis of 16th-century cadences, modal analysis according to Zarlino's theory, etc. At the user's request, other theoretical models can be added⁷. All comments and annotations are signed, dated and use unique identifiers to identify the musical objects to which they relate.

The selection and annotation system makes a significant contribution to musicology and musical analysis on several levels. The concepts associated with the selections have been formally defined, which, from a methodological point of view, lays the foundations for clarifying the underlying theoretical assumptions. Any musical mode annotated with the "Zarlino" model has for instance a certain number of structural properties explicitly defined in the corresponding ontology. This formal definition lays the foundations for the open sharing and re-use of the annotations in other studies.

The annotation system enables the iterative comparison of different analytical methods, thus helping to identify how the understanding of a work changes and/or is completed by the use of different models, for example harmonic

⁷It is planned that the user will be able to freely add their own models in a new version of the interface.

The image shows a musical score interface with an annotation sidebar. The score is for a five-part vocal setting, with parts for Canto, Alto, Tenore, Quinto, and Basso. The lyrics are in Italian. The annotation sidebar on the right is open, showing a 'Sub individual with 0 items' section with a 'CANCEL' button and a 'Comment...' field. Below this is an 'Individual with 3 items' section, which contains three concepts: 'C Bassizans_B', 'C Ultima', and 'C Penultima'. Each concept is represented by a blue button with a 'C' icon. There is also a 'Comment...' field at the bottom of the sidebar.

Figure 4.7: Analytical annotation of a clausula in a cadence

hundreds of pieces, such as the analytical corpus of Terpsichore's dances. In addition, it is planned in the medium term that annotations can be produced by machine learning from the human annotated corpora. The annotation system will thus establish a continuous and productive cycle between machine and human annotation.

[1] It is planned that the user will be able to freely add their own models in a new version of the interface.

5 Compliance to the FAIR principles

This software deliverable concerns the production of tools for annotating and citing research outputs. The main focus is the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO), a collection of methods and tools for organising, collecting, and publishing research outputs. The tools and methods are **Executable**, **Re-Usable Software** and **Data** (schema specifications).

The documentation of software components are in GitHub and are also released in Zenodo ensuring re-usability and exploitation by the Polifonia community (and beyond).

List all components related to this DL

name	REECO Annotation Schema
component-id	reeco-annotation-schema
type	Schema
work-package	WP1, WP5
related-components	reeco-jekyll, reeco-python, reeco-website-action, reeco-web-repo-validator
licence	Apache-2.0
contributors	Enrico Daga, Marilea Daquino, Marco Ratta, Andrea Scharnhorst
link	https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-annotation-schema
release-version	v0.1
doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655170

name	REECO Python
component-id	reeco-python
type	Schema
work-package	WP1, WP5
related-components	reeco-jekyll, reeco-annotation-schema, reeco-website-action, reeco-web-repo-validator
licence	Apache-2.0
contributors	Enrico Daga, Marco Ratta
link	https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-python https://pypi.org/project/reeco/ (PyPi)
release-version	v0.1
doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655153

name	REECO Jekyll
component-id	reeco-jekyll
type	Schema
work-package	WP1, WP5
related-components	reeco-python, reeco-annotation-schema, reeco-website-action, reeco-web-repo-validator
licence	Apache-2.0
contributors	Enrico Daga, Raphaël Fournier-S'niehotta, Damian Dadswell, Harriett Cornish, Marco Ratta
link	https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-python https://pypi.org/project/reeco/ (PyPi)
release-version	v0.1
doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655153

name	REECO Web Repo Validator
component-id	reeco-jekyll
type	Schema
work-package	WP1, WP5
related-components	reeco-python, reeco-annotation-schema, reeco-website-action, reeco-jekyll
licence	Apache-2.0
contributors	Enrico Daga
link	https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-web-repo-validator (Github) https://reeco.kmi.open.ac.uk (online)
release-version	v0.1
doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655175

name	REECO Github Action
component-id	reeco-website-action
type	Schema
work-package	WP1, WP5
related-components	reeco-python, reeco-annotation-schema, reeco-jekyll
licence	Apache-2.0
contributors	Enrico Daga
link	https://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-web-repo-validator (Github) https://reeco.kmi.open.ac.uk (online)
release-version	v0.1
doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655175

All components adhere to the Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science [3].

6 Conclusions

In this (software) deliverable, we described the Research Ecosystem Framework (REECO), a suite of tools supporting the management of research objects in context. This includes to manage data in their context, but also goes beyond data. The context is interdisciplinary and innovative research collaborations executed in project funding. One could say that the REECO is a machine executable Data Management Plan. However, the aspiration of this approach goes beyond Data Management. It concerns in essence making explicit what are the fundamental knowledge units and actions needed in these kind of research collaborations.

Collaborations funded by projects come with their own dynamics. Their planning is already structured (usually in Workpackages and Tasks) and their accountability (scientifically and financially) is also regulated by a set of Milestones, Deliverables, and PersonMonths allocated to produce the promised output.

The REECO approach bridges between processes of knowledge production which are specific to each set of research questions, and the more administrative processes in the management of staff and other resources during research. It builds on formalisations which have been already proposed for the former (namely to describe concrete ingredients as research objects and to also define their inter-relatedness). It also embraces the formal structures existing for the latter, for project management. It does so by:

- finding the right agglomeration of research objects and relations - named components.
- providing a set of tools to create, annotate, evaluate and archive components
- creating an overview about the components and enable to monitor them

More concretely, the REECO encompasses the categories Data, Tools (software and applications) and Reports. The latter are representing specific documentations of output but also requirements which function as input for the research process. This way, the REECO extends Research Data Management, to managing Data in their Context.

In this DL we describe the generic approach of the REECO together with its first concrete implementation for the Polifonia project, in form of the Polifonia Ecosystem. This way, the REECO is made available for reuse and extension to future projects. For the Polifonia *use case or implementation* we also included details from a selection of Polifonia applications which support other ways in which musical data can be referenced and cited.

In Section 1 (see Table 2.1) , we listed the REECO objectives and here we summarise how we addressed them (see Table 6.1.

The essence of the REECO is to find - collectively - a middle ground to identify those research components which form the cornerstones of a specific knowledge production process. The power of a formalisation of such cornerstones - named *components* in the REECO approach - is that main paths of transferring, combining and creating knowledge become visible, tangible and traceable. Finally, although we designed a rich metadata schema, metadata curation is considered in an open-ended way, where projects can extend the schema to incorporate new aspects and domain-specific concerns.

Table 6.1: Objections versus Solutions

Support Research Data Management	Data Management Plan Version 3 [4]
Present an organised view of project outputs to foster reuse beyond the project	http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-website-action A custom Github action to automate the generation of the ecosystem knowledge graph and website
Support an aware reuse of outputs by including copyright and licencing information	Specific field in the Annotation Schema http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-annotation-schema (see also [10])
Lower the barrier for users (developers, data scientists, researchers) to provide extensive metadata, building on good practices in (open-source) data/software development and research open data publishing	Python Library http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-python A software library in python to help processing and validating annotations. This is reused by various tools.
Facilitate the generation of metadata in different forms, to plug-in existing open science distributed infrastructures	Web Validator http://github.com/reeco-framework/reeco-web-repo-validator A utility to validate the annotations on a repository (running instance at http://reeco.kmi.open.ac.uk).

Bibliography

- [1] E. Daga, A. Meroño Peñuela, M. Daquino, F. Ciroku, E. Musumeci, M. Gurrieri, A. Scharnhorst, F. Admiraal, and R. Fournier-S'niehotta, "D1.3: Pilots development – collaborative methodology and tools (V1.0)," Tech. Rep., 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7712909>
- [2] F. Admiraal, A. Scharnhorst, E. Daga, M. Daquino, E. Musumeci, P. Kranenburg, C. Guillotel-Nothmann, M. Gurrieri, V. Presutti, M. Clementi, A. Meroño Peñuela, M. Turci, E. Marzi, A. Puglisi, and R. Fournier-S'niehotta, "D7.1 first data management plan," Aug. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6963585>
- [3] A. Scharnhorst, R. Van Horik, E. Daga, M. Daquino, E. Musumeci, P. Van Kranenburg, C. Guillotel-Nothmann, M. Gurrieri, V. Presutti, M. Clementi, A. Meroño Peñuela, M. Turci, E. Marzi, A. Puglisi, and R. Fournier-S'niehotta, "D7.2 data management plan (second version)," Feb. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7660299>
- [4] A. Scharnhorst, E. Daga, R. Fournier-S'niehotta, M. Gurrieri, J. de Berardinis, J. Mc Dermott, R. Tripodi, M. Daquino, G. Renda, A. Poltronieri, E. Musumeci, F. Magnani, P. van Kranenburg, C. Guillotel-Nothmann, T. Bottini, F. Ciroku, M. Clementi, A. Meroño Peñuela, M. Turci, E. Marzi, A. Puglisi, C. Uwasomba, J. Carvalho, A. Morales-Tirado, M. Bontje, R. de Groot, and V. Presutti, "D7.3 polifonia data management plan (final version)," Dec. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7660299>
- [5] P. Groth, A. Gibson, and J. Velterop, "The anatomy of a nanopublication," *Information services & use*, vol. 30, no. 1-2, pp. 51–56, 2010.
- [6] E. Daga, M. Daquino, R. Fournier-S'niehotta, C. Guillotel-Nothmann, and A. Scharnhorst, "Documenting the research process. opportunities and challenges for bibliometrics and information retrieval," in *Proceedings of the 13th International Workshop on Bibliometric-enhanced Information Retrieval*, I. F. P. M. G. C. S. Verberne, Ed. Zenodo, 2023, p. 17. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249512>
- [7] C. Guillotel-Nothmann, T. Bottini, V. Carriero, J. Carvalho, P. Cathé, F. Ciroku, E. Daga, M. Daquino, A. Davy-Rigaux, M. Gurrieri, P. Van Kemenade, E. Marzi, V. Presutti, and A. Scharnhorst, "D1.1 roadmap and pilot requirements 1st version," Tech. Rep., Sep. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7124253>
- [8] C. Guillotel-Nothmann, J. De Berardinis, T. Bottini, P. Cathé, E. Daga, M. Daquino, A. Davy-Rigaux, M. Gurrieri, P. Van Kranenburg, E. Marzi, J. McDermott, A. Meroño Peñuela, P. Mulholland, A. Scharnhorst, and R. Tripodi, "D1.2 roadmap and pilot requirements 2nd version," Tech. Rep., Sep. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7116561>
- [9] T. Pellegrini, G. Havur, S. Steyskal, O. Panasiuk, A. Fensel, V. Mireles, T. Thurner, A. Polleres, S. Kirrane, and A. Schönhofer, "Dalicc: a license management framework for digital assets," *Proceedings of the Internationales Rechtsinformatik Symposium (IRIS)*, vol. 10, 2019.
- [10] E. Daga, J. Carvalho, M. Gurrieri, and A. Scharnhorst, "D2.6: Ontology of licencing, ownership and conditions of use (v1.0)," Tech. Rep., Feb. 2023.
- [11] S. Peroni and D. Shotton, "The spar ontologies," in *The Semantic Web–ISWC 2018: 17th International Semantic Web Conference, Monterey, CA, USA, October 8–12, 2018, Proceedings, Part II 17*. Springer, 2018, pp. 119–136.
- [12] E. Daga, L. Asprino, A. Gangemi, and P. Mulholland, "Knowledge Graph Construction with a façade: a unified method to access heterogeneous data sources on the Web," *Transactions on Internet Technologies*, 2023.
- [13] E. Daga, A. Meroño Peñuela, M. Daquino, F. Ciroku, E. Musumeci, M. Gurrieri, A. Scharnhorst, F. Admiraal, and R. Fournier-S'niehotta, "D1.3: Pilots development – collaborative methodology and tools (V1.0)," Mar. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7712909>

- [14] M. Daquino, A. Meroño Peñuela, C. Guillotel-Nothmann, and P. Mulholland, “D1.9: Polifonia web portal - 1st version (v1.0),” Sep. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7116711>
- [15] J. de Berardinis, V. A. Carriero, N. Jain, N. Lazzari, A. Meroño-Peñuela, A. Poltronieri, and V. Presutti, “The polifonia ontology network: Building a semantic backbone for musical heritage,” in *International Semantic Web Conference*. Springer, 2023, pp. 302–322.
- [16] F. Pachet, “Knowledge management and musical metadata,” *Idea Group*, vol. 12, 2005.
- [17] C. Sintonio and A. Nucciarelli, *The impact of blockchain on the music industry*. Calgary: International Telecommunications Society (ITS), 2018.
- [18] J. de Berardinis, V. Carriero, A. Meroño-Peñuela, A. Poltronieri, and V. Presutti, “The music meta ontology: a flexible semantic model for the interoperability of music metadata,” in *Proc. of the 24th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, 2023.
- [19] Y. Raimond, S. Abdallah, M. Sandler, and F. Giasson, “The Music Ontology,” in *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR 2007)*, Vienna, Austria, Sep. 2007.
- [20] M. Achichi, R. Bailly, C. Cecconi, M. Destandau, K. Todorov, and R. Troncy, “Doremus: Doing reusable musical data,” in *ISWC: International Semantic Web Conference*, 2015.
- [21] J. de Berardinis, A. Meroño-Peñuela, A. Poltronieri, and V. Presutti, “Choco: a chord corpus and a data transformation workflow for musical harmony knowledge graphs,” *Scientific Data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 641, 2023.
- [22] —, “The harmonic memory: a knowledge graph of harmonic patterns as a trustworthy framework for computational creativity,” in *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023*, 2023, pp. 3873–3882.
- [23] J. de Berardinis, A. M. Peñuela, A. Poltronieri, V. Presutti, R. Fournier-S'niehotta, P. Rigaux, and T. Zhu, “D1.5 intermediate validation reports for pilots: Interlink and facets (v1.0),” European Commission, The Polifonia consortium, Tech. Rep., 2022.
- [24] A. M. Peñuela, J. de Berardinis, I. Reklós, and E. Simperl, “D2.5 methods for interlinking knowledge graphs,” European Commission, The Polifonia consortium, Tech. Rep., 2024.
- [25] A. Morales Tirado, J. Carvalho, and E. Daga, “polifonia-project/meetups-knowledge-graph: V1.0,” December 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7924618>
- [26] A. M. Tirado and E. Daga, “polifonia-project/meetups_pilot: v0.1,” Jul. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6866860>
- [27] A. Morales Tirado, J. Carvalho, P. Mulholland, and E. Daga, “Musical meetups: a knowledge graph approach for historical social network analysis,” in *Proceedings of the ESWC 2023 Workshops and Tutorials co-located with 20th European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2023)*, May 2023.
- [28] A. Morales Tirado, J. Carvalho, A. Graciotti, and E. Daga, “D4.4: Software for knowledge extraction from text – entities – 2nd version,” Oct 2023.

```
---
container-id: fabulous
type: Project
name: The Fabulous Project
description: The Fabulous Project is a very important part of the ecosystem.
image: http://www.example.org/myimage.png
logo: http://www.example.org/logo.png
work-package:
- WP1
- WP2
pilot:
- ThePilot
project: a-fabulous-project
funder:
- name: Lorem Ipsum Funder
  url: https://www.lorem-ipsum-funder.org
  grant-agreement: "01234556"
credits: "This project has received funding from the Lorem Ipsum Funder research
and innovation programme under grant agreement 01234556."
bibliography:
- main-publication: "Brown, L. (2019). The Role of Parenting Styles in Child
Development. Child Development Perspectives, 13(3), 145-153."
- publication:
- "Smith, J. (2020). The Impact of Social Media on Mental Health. Journal of
Psychology and Behavioral Sciences, 15(2), 45-62."
- has-part:
- fabulous-component-source-code
- fabulous-docs
- fabulous-tutorials
- fabulous-evaluation
- fabulous-requirements
- fabulous-dataset
---

# The Fabulous Project

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor
incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis
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fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in
culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

[Link to the website] (http://www.example.org)
```

Figure 1: Example of container description and annotation in Markdown.

```
---
component-id: fabulous-component-source-code
type: Software
name: The Fabulous Source Code
description: Source code of The Fabulous
logo: https://www.example.org/logo.png
work-package:
- WP1
- WP2
pilot:
- ThePilot
project: a-fabulous-project
resource: https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repo1/releases
demo: https://www.example.org/fabulous/demo
release-date: 2023/01/18
release-number: v1.0-alpha
release-link: https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repo1/releases/tag/v0.8.1
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.000000
changelog: https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repo1/releases/tag/v0.8.1
licence:
- Apache-2.0
copyright: "Copyright (c) 2023 Fabolous, Inc"
contributors:
- A developer <http://www.example.org>
related-components:
- informed-by:
  - fabulous-requirements
- use-case:
  - fabulous-uc
- story:
  - fabulous-story
- persona:
  - fabulous-persona
- documentation:
  - fabulous-component-docs
  - fabulous-component-tutorials
- extends:
  - "A Java project Jena https://www.example.org"
- reuses:
  - "Apache Camel https://camel.apache.org/"
- generated-by:
  - The AI code generator http://www.my-software-factory.com
- evaluated-in:
  - fabulous-evaluation
credits: "This project has received funding from the Lorem Ipsum Funder research
and innovation programme under grant agreement 01234556."
---

# The Fabulous Component

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor
incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis
nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

41

[Link to the website] (http://www.example.org)
```

Figure 2: Example of component description and annotation in Markdown.